

Guidelines for evaluating Adequacy and Fluency

Objective

This section contains the guidelines evaluators should follow to evaluate Adequacy and Fluency in translations. The goal of these guidelines, which contain explanations and examples of each score, serve to homogenize criteria of evaluators to obtain reproducible and reliable results in translation quality evaluation.

Fluency

Fluency can be understood as to what extent the translation is **“one that is well-formed grammatically, contains correct spellings, adheres to common use of terms, titles and names, is intuitively acceptable and can be sensibly interpreted by a native speaker”** (Linguistic Data Consortium).

Fluency must be evaluated first, before reading the source text, to evaluate whether the translation reads natural in the target language. Why? It is worth stressing that a translation may be flawlessly fluent (that is, the translation may be perfectly-formed and follow all the target language rules), but may have adequacy problems (e.g., may contain only partially the meaning of the source sentence)¹. After the evaluation of Fluency, you can then evaluate Adequacy (more details on how to evaluate Adequacy below).

In the table below, Fluency scores are defined and some examples of their evaluation are provided:

SCORE 1 - INCOMPREHENSIBLE	
The translation is poorly written and nothing can be understood and/or the grammar and syntactical rules of the target language are not respected at all.	
ENGLISH SOURCE TEXT	SPANISH TRANSLATION
Record-high inflation in the Eurozone for October.	El Deflación muy muy muy permanece contento el.
Men jailed for life for murder of Sheffield solicitor.	Abogado mujeres muerte Sheffield cárcel años años años.

SCORE 2 - DISFLUENT	
The sentence is incorrectly written and is difficult to understand and/or the grammar and syntactical rules of the target language are scarcely respected. Less than 50% of the translation can be understood.	
ENGLISH SOURCE TEXT	SPANISH TRANSLATION
Dishonest solicitor ‘too embarrassed’ to tell bosses of her mistake	Deshonesta abogada no contar sus error a su jefes por avergonzada
New lord chancellor leads events to mark opening of the legal year	Comienzar de los canciller porque para empezar los año de juicio

¹ You can find more exceptions and further explanations in the section Additional Examples.

SCORE 3 - GOOD	
The translation is understood partially because it is fluent, but has some minor mistakes in terms of grammar and syntactical rules of the target language. More than 50% of the translation can be understood.	
ENGLISH SOURCE TEXT	SPANISH TRANSLATION
In most cases, the enquiry will not extend beyond an assessment of the parties' needs.	En la mayoría de caso, la investigación no viajará más allá de una evaluación de las necesidades del parte.
Drawing a line between marital and non-marital assets is not always easy.	Trazar una raya apartadora entre los bienes conyugales y no matrimonio no siempre es fácil.

SCORE 4 - FLAWLESS	
The sentence is very fluent and contains no errors , and the grammar and syntactical rules of the target language are completely respected .	
ENGLISH SOURCE TEXT	SPANISH TRANSLATION
Record-high inflation in the Eurozone for October.	Inflación récord en la zona euro en octubre.
Which nuclear weapons could Putin use against Ukraine?	¿Qué armas nucleares podría utilizar Putin contra Ucrania?

Adequacy

Adequacy can be understood as “**how much of the meaning expressed in the gold-standard translation or the source is also expressed in the target translation**” (Linguistic Data Consortium).

In the table below, Adequacy scores are defined and some examples of their evaluation are provided:

SCORE 1 - NONE	
None of the meaning in the source is contained in the translation.	
ENGLISH SOURCE TEXT	SPANISH TRANSLATION
Record-high inflation in the Eurozone for October.	El EURIBOR toca mínimos anuales en la última revisión.
Ms. Eileen Patterson has been newly appointed as deputy chair of the board.	Don Eileen Patterson acaba de ser destituido como tesorero del partido político.

SCORE 2 - LITTLE	
Small fragments of the meaning in the source are contained in the translation. Less than 50% of the total meaning in the source is contained in the translation.	
ENGLISH SOURCE TEXT	SPANISH TRANSLATION
As a non-executive director, he will contribute to the good governance of the Department of Health.	Como directora ejecutiva, contribuirá a la buena gobernanza del gobierno nacional.
Our new partners are highly experienced advisers in sectors impacted by the impending departure of the UK from the European Union.	Nuestros nuevos socios tienen mucha experiencia en los problemas de independencia entre Irlanda del Norte y la República de Irlanda.

SCORE 3 - MOST	
Almost all the meaning in the source is contained in the translation. More than 50% of the total meaning of the source is contained in the translation.	
ENGLISH SOURCE TEXT	SPANISH TRANSLATION
Record-high inflation in the Eurozone for October.	Inflación récord en la zona euro.
Both appointments are for a period of three years, beginning 1 October 2022, with the possibility of an extension to a maximum of six years.	Ambos nombramientos tienen una vigencia de tres años, pero existe la posibilidad de extenderlos hasta un período máximo de seis.

SCORE 4 - EVERYTHING	
All the meaning in the source is contained in the translation, no more, no less.	
ENGLISH SOURCE TEXT	SPANISH TRANSLATION
Record-high inflation in the Eurozone for October.	Inflación récord en la zona euro en octubre.
Which nuclear weapons could Putin use against Ukraine?	¿Qué armas nucleares podría utilizar Putin contra Ucrania?

Additional Examples

This section contains some further explanations in some additional examples. After some iterations, these examples have shown to be problematic, so we are adding them here so you know how to score each segment in case you encounter any of these types of segments.

FLUENCY IS INDEPENDENT FROM ADEQUACY	
Remember that you should assess Fluency without considering Adequacy.	
ENGLISH SOURCE TEXT	SPANISH TRANSLATION
WHEREAS the SUPPLIER wishes to engage the AGENT to sell his products in the territory of Spain;	LAS PARTES EXPONEN QUE el PROVEEDOR desea contratar al PROVEEDOR para que venda sus productos en España;
<p>In the example above, both “SUPPLIER” and “AGENT” are translated as “PROVEEDOR”. This is a wrong in terms of Adequacy, and therefore the Adequacy score should be SCORE 3 – MOST.</p> <p>Nevertheless, in terms of Fluency, the translation reads completely natural and the Fluency score should be SCORE 4 – FLAWLESS.</p> <p>Thus, Fluency should be assessed independently from Adequacy.</p>	

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DEALING WITH PERCENTAGES OF APPROPRIATENESS –
ADEQUACY IS DEPENDENT FROM FLUENCY

This table explains in detail **how to assess the percentage of appropriateness in Fluency and Adequacy in terms of the +/-50% threshold**. Fluency mistakes are marked in red; Adequacy mistakes are marked in blue. Unlike the previous additional example, **Adequacy is dependent from Fluency**.

ENGLISH SOURCE TEXT	SPANISH TRANSLATION
<p>The AGENT <u>shall in and about the execution of his activity make</u> every effort to safeguard <u>the interests</u> of the SUPPLIER, <u>in conformity with</u> the best business practice.</p>	<p><u>Mientras actividad ejercer</u>, el REPRESENTANTE <u>tener que hacer</u> todo lo posible para proteger <u>las intereses</u> del PROVEEDOR, <u>así como conforme</u> con las mejores prácticas empresariales.</p>
<p>The AGENT <u>shall in and about the execution of his activity make</u> every effort to safeguard <u>the interests</u> of the SUPPLIER, <u>in conformity with</u> the best business practice.</p>	<p><u>Mientras actividad ejercer</u>, el REPRESENTANTE <u>tener que</u> hacer todo lo posible para proteger <u>las intereses</u> del PROVEEDOR, <u>así como conforme</u> con las mejores prácticas empresariales.</p>

In terms of Fluency (red), +50% of the source words are marked in red, which means that they have fluency problems in the translation. Thus, the appropriate Fluency score for this segment would be SCORE 2 – DISFLUENT. The translation does not flow in Spanish, and cannot be read naturally.

In terms of Adequacy (blue), most of the translation can be understood. Nevertheless, though the implied meaning of the translation may provide the reader with correct information of the source, the wording of the translation is not correct, and therefore not adequate.

If the meaning of the translation is correct, but the wording is not appropriate, then the translation is not adequate and Adequacy should be penalized. In the above example, by reading the translation you can devise what the source meant in “Mientras actividad ejercer”, though this is not properly written. Thus, by following this guideline, +50% of the source words are marked in blue, which means that they have adequacy problems in the translation. The appropriate Adequacy score for this segment would be SCORE 2 – LITTLE.

VERY IMPORTANT: though there may be non-adequate but fluent translations, for a translation to be adequate, fluency should also be evaluated. Thus, adequate translation should also be fluent.